

(a) Raman spectra of electrodeposited MoS₂ on FTO, acquired in 42 different points. (b) A_{1g} peak position versus E_{2g} peak position. (c) Absorbance spectra of MoS₂ deposited at different concentrations, compared with the reference FTO/Glass. (d) Room temperature photoluminescence spectra of MoS₂ on FTO/Glass substrate recorded in 42 points of the sample

The relative E_{2G}/A_{1g} ratio calculated from the Raman results can be used to distinguish between basal- and edge-oriented MoS₂, as shown in refs [1,2]. Values of the E_{2G}/A_{1g} ratio around 0.7 typically indicate deposited horizontal MoS₂ layers basal oriented. Values of about 0.5 correspond to vertically or edge oriented MoS₂ layers. The figure shows E_{2G}/A_{1g} as calculated for MoS₂ electrodeposited with low, medium or high concentration. The average values are in the range 0.53 – 0.7, therefore suggesting that the MoS₂ flakes are oriented mainly horizontally, although some flakes, characterized by lower values of the ratio E_{2G}/A_{1g} (0.4-0.5) may be vertically aligned. However, in our case the substrate is not flat since the FTO is textured, and we believe that the MoS₂ flakes locally align to the substrate. This is clearly shown in the SEM/STEM micrographs shown in the next slide.

FTO substrate before MoS₂ deposition

(left) Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrograph of the surface of the FTO substrate on glass before MoS₂ electrodeposition, (right) SEM micrograph of the surface of the FTO after MoS₂ electrodeposition,

Scanning Transmission Electron (STEM) micrograph of the ITO/MoO₃/MoS₂/FTO/glass sample in cross section; STEM image at higher magnification evidencing the layered crystalline structure of MoS₂; STEM analyses of the ITO/MoO₃/MoS₂/FTO/glass sample in cross section in HAADF at high magnification, and corresponding EELS spectra showing the S, Mo, In, Sn, and O edges, taken in the ITO, MoO₃, MoS₂, and FTO layers.

I-V characteristics of the ITO/MoS₂/FTO and ITO/MoO₃/MoS₂/FTO heterostructures, together with the ITO/FTO and ITO/MoO₃/FTO reference junctions without MoS₂.

Photoelectric response of the REFERENCE ITO/FTO and ITO/MoO₃/FTO heterostructure samples illuminated by a red laser source at varying power intensities. In all the figures, the time axis is set so that the laser is switched on/off at 0 s/5 s, 10 s/15 s, 20 s/25 s, etc., i.e., at a frequency of 0.1 Hz and with a duty cycle of 50%.

Photoelectric response of the TCO / MoS₂ /TCO heterostructure samples illuminated by a red laser source at varying power intensities. Same conditions as reference samples

Photocurrent, equal to the average difference between current in conditions of dark and light, as a function of the photocurrent measured by the silicon photodiode for the ITO/MoS₂/FTO (left) and the ITO/MoO₃/MoS₂/FTO junction (right) for various effective thicknesses of MoS₂ and compared to the references without MoS₂.

Current vs time obtained by switching on and off the laser light in an ITO/MoO₃/MoS₂/FTO junction at various bias levels.

Photocurrent amplitude of the ITO/MoO₃/MoS₂/FTO/glass at different positive and negative bias voltages. The data represent the average values obtained from multiple on/off cycles measured at each polarization value.